

Speed of sound and related parameters of epoxy resin of Schiff base solutions at 303, 308 and 313 K

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Abstract : The density, viscosity and speed of sound (2 MHz) in THF and epoxy resin solutions have been investigated to understand molecular interactions at 303, 308 and 313 K. Various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters such as specific acoustical impedance (Z), adiabatic compressibility (κ_a), Van der Waals constant (b), internal pressure (π), viscous relaxation time (τ), free volume (V_f), intermolecular free path length (L_f) and classical absorption coefficient ($(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$) have been determined using density (ρ), viscosity (η), speed of sound (U) data and are correlated with concentration. A fairly good to excellent correlation between a given parameter and concentration is observed. Studied acoustical and thermodynamic parameters indicated existence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions. Gibbs free energy of activation (ΔG^*) is found both concentration and temperature dependent. Both enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) are found concentration dependent.

Keywords : Density, viscosity, speed of sound, molecular interactions.

Introduction

Epoxy resins are most widely used in land, marine and space transportations, automobile and electrical components, rehabilitation, pollution control equipments, adhesives, laminates, printed circuit boards, molds for casting and composite materials, in the aerospace and aircraft industries, etc.¹⁻⁴. The characteristic excellent physico-chemical properties of epoxy resins make them suitable for an increasing number of engineering applications such as those requiring high strength and stiffness, good dielectric behavior, resistance to chemicals, low shrinkage during cure, etc.

The knowledge of density, viscosity and speed of sound and derived acoustical and thermodynamic parameters are very useful in studying organic liquids and their mixtures, aqueous, nonaqueous, electrolytic and polymeric solutions. These parameters furnish information about ionic, covalent, charge transfer, hydrogen bonding, ionic-dipole, hydrophilic interactions and hence molecular and structural properties of the liquid solutions, which are very important for polymer processing and their uses⁵⁻¹⁴. Molecular interactions result into conformational changes and hence change in the solution viscosity, osmotic pressure, light scattering, etc. Recently we have published

speed of sound and related parameters for epoxy resins¹⁵⁻¹⁷. To the best of our knowledge no work has been reported on speed of sound and related acoustical and thermodynamic parameters of epoxy resin of symmetric Schiff base containing cyclohexyl as a cardo (Latin meaning a loop) group (I). The resin is only soluble in THF and possesses limited solubility. In the present work we have reported the effect of concentration, temperature and nature of solvent on molecular interactions occurring in the epoxy resin solutions. The study is carried out over a narrow temperature range from 298 to 313 K and concentration range from 0.5 to 2 wt%.

Scheme 1. (ESDI)

Experimental

Reagents and techniques :

Tetrahydrofuran (THF) (Loba Chemie, Mumbai) used in the present investigation was of laboratory grade and

was further purified by fractional distillation¹⁸. 1,1'-Bis(4-aminophenyl)cyclohexane based bisphenol¹⁹ and its epoxy resin (ESDI) (Scheme 1)²⁰ were synthesized and crystallized/purified according to reported methods. The resin used in the present work had 4020 weight average molecular weight.

Measurements :

The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of sound (U) measurements on THF and ESDI solutions (0.5 to 2 wt%) were carried out at 303, 308 and 313 \pm 0.1 K (Nova Instruments Model NV8550E, Ahmedabad) by using specific gravity bottle, Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer and Mittal Enterprise Interferometer (New Delhi), Model No. F-81 operating at 2 MHz, respectively. The ρ , η and U measurements were accurate to ± 0.1 kg m⁻³, ± 0.01 mPa s and $\pm 0.1\%$, respectively.

Theoretical equations for acoustical parameters :

Experimental data such as density, viscosity and speed of sound were used to derive various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters according to following theoretical equations :

Specific acoustical impedance (Z) :

$$Z = U\rho \quad (1)$$

Adiabatic compressibility (κ_a) :

Adiabatic compressibility (κ_a) can be evaluated according to Newton and Laplace :

$$\kappa_a = \frac{1}{U^2\rho} \quad (2)$$

Van der Waals constant (b)²¹ :

$$b = \frac{M}{\rho} \left[1 - \left[\frac{RT}{MU^2} \right] \left[\sqrt{1 + \frac{MU^2}{3RT}} - 1 \right] \right] \quad (3)$$

where M is the apparent molecular weight of the solution, R is the gas constant and T is the absolute temperature.

Internal pressure (π)²² :

$$\pi = b'RT \left(\frac{K\eta}{U} \right)^{1/2} \frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M^{7/6}} \quad (4)$$

where b' is the packing factor (2) and K is a constant

(4.28×10^9). The internal pressure depends on temperature, density, speed of sound and specific heat at a constant pressure.

Free volume (V_f)²² :

$$V_f = \left[\frac{MU}{K\eta} \right]^{3/2} \quad (5)$$

Inter molecular free path length (L_f)²³ :

$$L_f = K'(\kappa_a)^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where K' is the Jacobson's constant [$K' = (93.875 + 0.375T) \times 10^{-8}$] and it is temperature dependent. κ_a is the adiabatic compressibility.

Classical absorption coefficient (α/f^2)_{cl}⁷ :

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2} \right)_{cl} = \frac{8\pi^2\eta}{3U^3\rho} \quad (7)$$

Viscous relaxation time (τ)⁷ :

The resistance offered by viscous force in the flow of sound wave appears as a classical absorption associated with it is the viscous relaxation time :

$$\tau = \frac{4\eta}{3\rho U^2} \quad (8)$$

Thermodynamic parameters⁷ :

Free energy of activation (ΔG^*), enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) can be determined by using viscous relaxation time data at different concentrations and temperatures :

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \frac{kT}{h} e^{-\frac{\Delta G_f^*}{RT}} \quad (9)$$

$$\ln \frac{1}{\tau T} = \ln \frac{k}{h} + \frac{\Delta S^*}{R} - \frac{\Delta H^*}{RT} \quad (10)$$

where k is the Boltzmann constant and h is the Planck's constant.

Results and discussion

Experimentally derived quantities namely ρ , η and U of THF and ESDI solutions at three different temperatures are presented in Table 1. The densities of the solutions decreased linearly with both concentration of ESDI

Table 1. The density (ρ), viscosity (η) and speed of sound (U) data of ESDI in THF at 303, 308 and 313 K

Conc. (wt%)	Density ρ (kg m ⁻³)	Viscosity η (mPa s)	U (m s ⁻¹) ($F = 2$ MHz)
303 K			
0	883.3	0.496	1232.8
0.5	892.2	0.517	1237.2
1.0	891.6	0.532	1240.4
1.5	890.4	0.549	1244.0
2.0	889.3	0.567	1247.6
308 K			
0	881.3	0.442	1225.6
0.5	890.1	0.477	1230.0
1.0	889.2	0.490	1232.0
1.5	888.0	0.502	1237.2
2.0	887.1	0.520	1241.6
313 K			
0	875.5	0.396	1212.4
0.5	889.3	0.443	1216.0
1.0	887.8	0.454	1218.8
1.5	886.5	0.466	1220.8
2.0	885.7	0.477	1224.0

and temperature. Both viscosities and speed of sound increased linearly with concentration of ESDI and decreased with temperature. The ρ , η and U data were correlated with concentration of ESDI and temperature. Excellent correlation between ρ and concentration of ESDI, η and concentration of ESDI, U and concentration of ESDI is observed (Regression coefficient $R^2 = 0.992 - 0.999$) at three different temperatures. The variation of η and U with concentration of ESDI and temperature are considerably more than that of ρ due to specific molecular interactions such as association, deassociation, unfolding, expansion, etc. occurring in the solutions. Intermolecular motion in solution is affected by molecular interactions²⁴. Attractive forces resulted into molecular association (solvation), i.e. modification of the structure of the solute. Molecular association leads to changes in both the apparent molecular volume as well as mass and hence the density of the solution. The decrease of ρ , η and U with temperature indicated decrease of cohesive forces⁵⁻¹⁷. Van der Waals, H-bonding, dipolar and London type interactions resulted into the aggregation of the solvent molecules around solute molecules and as a result structural modification took place^{24,15-17}. The nature of solvent and

the solute are responsible in determining all transport and other properties of the solutions.

Various acoustical and thermodynamic parameters of pure THF and ESDI solutions were derived by using ρ , η and U data at different temperatures. These parameters were correlated with concentration of ESDI and the least square plots are presented in Figs. 1-7. Specific acoustical impedance (Z) (Fig. 1), b (not shown graphically), V_f (Fig. 4), $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ (Fig. 6) and τ (Fig. 7) were increased linearly with concentration of ESDI and decreased with temperature except Z at 308 and 313 K and V_f . Both Z and V_f varied nonlinearly with concentration of ESDI and temperature. Practically no temperature effect was observed on b . κ_a (Fig. 2), π (Fig. 3) and L_f (Fig. 5) were decreased linearly with concentration of ESDI and increased with temperature. The increase of Z , b , V_f , τ and $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ with concentration of ESDI and decrease with temperature confirmed increase of the cohesive forces and hence existence of strong molecular interactions.

Fig. 1. The plots of specific acoustical impedance (Z) against concentration (wt%) of ESDI in THF at 303, 308 and 313 K.

Fig. 2. The plots of adiabatic compressibility (κ_a) against concentration (wt%) of ESDI in THF at 303, 308 and 313 K.

Fig. 3. The plots of internal pressure (π) against concentration (wt%) of ESDI in THF at 303, 308 and 313 K.

Fig. 6. The plots of classical absorption co-efficient $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ against concentration (wt%) of ESDI in THF at 303, 308 and 313 K.

Fig. 4. The plots of free volume (V_f) against concentration (wt%) of ESDI in THF at 303, 308 and 313 K.

Fig. 7. The plots of viscous relaxation time (τ) against concentration (wt%) of ESDI in THF at 303, 308 and 313 K.

Fig. 5. The plots of inter molecular free path length (L_f) against concentration (wt%) of ESDI in THF at 303, 308 and 313 K.

Similarly decrease of κ_a , L_f and π with concentration of ESDI and increase with temperature confirmed increase of cohesive forces due to molecular interactions. Fairly good to excellent regression coefficients (R^2) are found for Z (0.943–0.998), κ_a (0.963–1.000), π (0.977), V_f

(0.999–1.000), L_f (0.963–1.000), $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ (0.997–0.999) and τ (0.998–0.999). We have also observed similar trends for other resin solutions also^{15–17}.

Variation of U in the solution depends on intermolecular free path length. When ultrasonic waves are incident on the solution, the molecules get perturbed. Since the medium has some elasticity and hence perturbed molecules regain their equilibrium positions. When a solute is added to a solvent, its molecules attract certain solvent molecules toward them. This process is known as solvation phenomena. The aggregation of solvent molecules around solute molecules supports strong solvent-solute interactions and considerable change in structural arrangement. Molecular interactions such as solvent-solute interactions, quantum mechanical dispersive forces and dielectric force may cause high degree of contraction or expansion. Molecular interactions affect transport properties of the solutions. The time lag between the excita-

tion and de-excitation processes is observed as an acoustical relaxation. This relaxation process is observed as either an increase in speed with frequency or a decrease in the $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ with frequency. Increasing temperature has two opposite effects namely structure formation (intermolecular association) and structure destruction. The structure forming tendency is primarily due to solvent-solute interactions, while destruction of structure formed previously is due to thermal fluctuations. When thermal energy is greater than that of interaction energy, it causes destruction of the structure formed previously^{15-17,24}. Dipole-dipole interactions of the opposite type favor structure formation, while of the same type favor structure breaking tendency. Azomethine and hydroxyl groups are polar groups besides other alkyl and aromatic groups, which may interact with THF molecules under a set of experimental conditions (concentration and temperature). Thus, studied parameters furnished solvophilic nature of the resin.

Thermodynamic parameters such as ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^* were determined according to eqs. (9) and (10) using viscous relaxation data as a function of concentration and temperature. The least square values of ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^* are presented in Table 2 from which it is observed that ΔG^* increased with concentration and decreased with increasing temperature. From the observed values of ΔG^* it can be presumed that condensation and absorption processes are concentration and temperature dependent. More over positive values of ΔG^* indicated that activated complexes possess more free energy of activation than that of individual resin molecules. Both ΔH^* and ΔS^* are found concentration dependent. Similar behavior was also observed in case of other Schiff base based resins solutions¹⁷.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG^* , ΔH^* and ΔS^*) derived using τ data of ESDI solutions

Conc. (wt%)	ΔG^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)			ΔH^* (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^* (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
	303 K	308 K	313 K		
0.5	2.92	2.84	2.80	6.56	11.98
1	2.98	2.90	2.86	6.83	12.72
1.5	3.05	2.95	2.92	7.08	13.31
2	3.12	3.02	2.96	7.77	15.38

Conclusions

A fairly good to excellent correlation between studied parameters with concentration and temperature was ob-

served. Derived acoustical and thermodynamic parameters confirmed existence of strong molecular interactions in the solutions, which found to depend on molecular structure of the resin. ΔG^* was observed both concentration and temperature dependent, while both ΔH^* and ΔS^* were observed concentration dependent.

Symbols

M = Apparent molecular weight of the solution (kg), ρ = Density (kg m⁻³), η = Viscosity (mPa s), U = Ultrasonic speed (m s⁻¹), R = Gas constant, Z = Specific acoustical impedance (kg m⁻² s⁻¹), κ_a = Adiabatic compressibility (Pa⁻¹), b = Van der Waals constant (m³), π = Internal pressure (Pa), τ = Viscous relaxation time (s), V_f = Free volume (m³), L_f = Intermolecular free path length (m), $(\alpha/f^2)_{cl}$ = Classical absorption coefficient (s² m⁻¹), ΔG^* = Gibb's free energy of activation (kJ mol⁻¹), ΔH^* = Enthalpy of activation (kJ mol⁻¹), ΔS^* = Entropy of activation (JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹), K' = Jacobson's constant, k = Boltzmann constant, h = Planck's constant, R^2 = Regression coefficients.

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